

DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF AN EJECTION MECHANISM FOR CEMENT-STABILISED BLOCKS IN AN IMPACT MOULDING MACHINE

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Abstract

Cement-stabilised blocks, when compacted using an impact-type moulding machine, are often difficult to eject due to high adhesive resistance between the block and the mould walls. This study presents the design and performance evaluation of a manually operated ejection mechanism for cement-stabilised blocks in an impact moulding machine. The mechanism employs a compound gear train, comprising 2:1 bevel gears followed by 3:1 spur gears, to drive a power screw capable of overcoming the 84.7 kN adhesive interface force. Ergonomic considerations were incorporated by adopting a maximum manual input force of 200 N, consistent with recommended sustained human effort, and a crank length of 0.37 m, derived from anthropometric data of Nigerian male workers. A removable breaker bar of 0.6 m radius was introduced to keep short-burst forces within safe two-hand operation limits during block–mould separation. With these provisions, the required 1737 Nm breakaway torque at the screw is achieved using 289.5 Nm input torque in short bursts and 74 Nm during sustained ejection. The system delivers an average ejection speed of 51.62 mm/min, with a total ejection time of 15.8 minutes per block. While safe and manufacturable for small-scale or off-grid use, mechanisation is recommended to improve throughput.

Keywords

*cement-stabilised blocks
ergonomic design
impact moulding machine
manual ejection
mechanism
screw jack system*

1. INTRODUCTION

An impact moulding (or dynamic compaction) machine is one that compacts a cement-sand-water mixture into a green block by repeatedly ramming a load (impactor) onto the mix from a predetermined height [1]. The primary purpose of using an impact moulding machine is to increase the density of the block through repeated ramming. According to [2], the compaction force and grain arrangement significantly influence block density and strength. Increased density, in turn, enhances cement effectiveness, resulting in stronger blocks that require less cement [3–4]

After compaction, the block must be ejected from the mould cavity without compromising its dimensional integrity or surface finish, and with minimal handling effort to allow easy transfer to the curing area. The common method of performing the task of block ejection in many small- and medium-scale applications is by using lever-based bottom ejection mechanisms due to their simplicity and rapid operation. Such systems can produce 200–300 blocks per hour [5].

However, the removal of compacted blocks from moulds after densification using an impact-type moulding method poses a more critical challenge. This is because blocks formed through dynamic compaction could only be ejected using a slow, steady force [1], whereas attempts at sudden ejection, which typifies lever-based ejection mechanisms, often cause the blocks to crack or become unusable. It was further observed in [1] that adhesion to the mould walls and frictional drag as blocks are ejected frequently marred the edges of the blocks, while multiple trials demonstrated that even under controlled conditions, the removal process was difficult and often resulted in significant defects. Moreover, [6] reported that the ejection of blocks moulded at a compaction ratio of 1.7:1, which would have produced a denser block, was extremely difficult and impossible with a lever-based ejection mechanism.

Since it is very difficult to remove these blocks safely without damaging the structure, impact moulding machines need an innovative manual ejection means that is optimised for effective block removal and the convenience of the operator. This will serve as an alternative to the usual lever systems. This study presents the design and analysis of a manual block ejection mechanism for an impact moulding machine using a power screw system. The goal is to make block removal safer, more comfortable, and more effective while keeping the structural integrity intact for cement-stabilized blocks that are more likely to get damaged during ejection.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. Materials Selection

Each component was evaluated based on its intended function, the types of forces it is expected to withstand during operation, and the environmental conditions it may be exposed to, such as moisture and surface wear (abrasion). Most of the parts of the impact moulding machine are subjected to shock load and repeated bending stress which can generate undesirable vibration and cause local damage to the structures. Therefore, low carbon steel, which is also called mild steel, was selected for the fabrication of most of the machine parts mainly because it is strong, tough, and readily machinable [7-8]. Apart from this, mild steel is cheap and available. Corrosion resistance was considered crucial for parts that came into contact with cementitious materials. The materials chosen for each part of the mechanism are described in Table 1.

Table 2.1: Criteria for selection of materials for impact moulding machine components

S/N	Component Name	Material Selected	Criteria for Selection
1	Mould box	Mild steel plate	High compressive strength, good damping, machinability, rigid
2	Bevel gears	Mild steel plate	Good machinability, high strength
3	Hollow shaft	Mild steel	Strong hardness, good toughness
4	Shaft	Mild steel plate	High strength, high torsional strength, machinability
5	Shaft bearing	Pillow block (high-carbon chromium steel)	Self-aligning, internally sealed
6	Hand crank	Cast iron	Moderate strength, weldability
7	Power screw	Mild steel	Moderate strength, weldability
8	Nut	Mild steel	Moderate strength, weldability
9	Hollow rectangular metal bar	Mild steel	Moderate strength, good machinability

2.2. Machine Description

Figure 1 presents the 3D overview of the impact moulding machine. As shown in Figure 2, the impact moulding machine compacts the cementitious mix (a combination of cement and sand or soil) inside the mould box through a manual ramming process. This is accomplished by turning the sector gear crank, which rotates the sector gear mounted on a solid shaft. The shaft is supported by two pillow bearings seated on the machine roof, providing stability and smooth rotation. As the sector gear turns, its teeth engage with those of a vertically mounted rack gear fixed to an impactor (heavy weight), causing the impactor (or ram) to be lifted.

Once the free (toothless) portion of the sector gear comes into contact with the rack gear, the engagement is lost, allowing the impactor to fall freely under the influence of gravity. The impactor strikes the mix in the mould box, and compacts it. This cycle of lifting and free-fall is repeated manually until the mix is sufficiently compacted into a green block.

To ensure proper vertical alignment of the impactor during this motion, the ram is connected to four upright guide pillars (impactor guide pillars) via impactor guide brackets. These impactor guide pillars serve to direct the vertical movement of the ram and prevent lateral displacement or wobbling during operation. 1

Block ejection is initiated by turning a crank (referred to as the bevel gear crank), which is connected via a shaft to the driving bevel gear (or vertical bevel gear). This vertical bevel gear meshes with and drives a horizontal bevel gear (driven bevel gear), which is rigidly welded to a rotating nut. As the driven bevel gear rotates, the nut, threadedly engaged with a power screw, also rotates, causing the screw to move axially. This axial motion is transmitted through a set of ejection (or push) rods attached to the plate welded to the upper end of the screw, pushing up an ejection plate located beneath the block pallet in the mould box. The ejection plate, in turn, lifts the block pallet along with the formed block, thereby ejecting the compacted block from the mould cavity.

Fig.1. 3D views of the Impact Moulding Machine from different perspectives

Fig.2. (a) Front view of the Impact Moulding Machine (b) Side view showing notable parts

The impact moulding machine is provided with a concrete base to withstand the repeated impact loads during compaction. It is designed to be pit-installed after fabrication. This installation method not only enhances the machine's overall stability and rigidity by embedding its base into the ground, but also positions the handwheel at an ergonomic operating height, thereby improving operator comfort during the ejection cycle. By reducing the machine's operating height in this way, the need for step platforms or elevated working positions is eliminated.

2.3. Design Considerations and Assumptions

2.3.1 Design Considerations

The design of the block ejection mechanism was guided by several engineering considerations and assumptions to ensure functionality, safety, durability, and ease of use. These are outlined as follows:

a. Load Capacity

The mechanism must withstand the maximum load exerted by the compacted block, including the weight of the cementitious material, adhesion forces between the mix and the mould walls, frictional resistance, and any additional operational forces. A safety factor was incorporated to account for unexpected overload conditions.

b. Ergonomics and Usability

The crank handle was designed with ergonomic considerations to minimize operator fatigue. Its length was optimized to reduce the input effort while providing sufficient torque for lifting the load. A comfortable grip was integrated to improve user experience during repetitive manual operation.

c. Mechanical Advantage

A suitable balance between mechanical advantage and operational speed was considered. A trade-off analysis informed the selection of transmission elements to ensure effective force multiplication without compromising speed and efficiency.

d. Safety Features

The design includes a self-locking feature to prevent accidental lowering of the ejected block. A mechanical stop was also included to prevent overextension, which could cause structural damage or component misalignment during operation.

e. Precision and Alignment

Tight tolerances were maintained to ensure alignment of moving parts and to prevent premature wear, misalignment, or inefficient operation. Mechanical guides were incorporated to maintain motion accuracy.

2.3.1 Design Assumptions

The following assumptions were made in the design of the ejection mechanism:

- a. The mould box dimensions are fixed at 450 mm × 150 mm × 225 mm to match the size of a standard solid block, and the box is constructed to provide adequate strength and a smooth internal surface to facilitate easy ejection.
- b. The mechanism is manually operated using a hand crank that supplies the required torque and input power.
- c. All structural components, including frames, mounts, and fasteners, are arranged compactly to support operational loads and preserve structural integrity.
- d. The design assumes that regular access for maintenance and lubrication will be available, with removable parts and service openings provided for ease of upkeep.

2.4. Design Analysis of the Ejection Mechanism

The mechanism is designed to deliver sufficient force to eject the green block from the mould box cavity. Therefore, the force to be overcome as the power screw moves upward vertically is calculated in the following sections.

2.4.1. Force of Adhesion

The formula for force of adhesion, F_a is obtained from the general stress formula ($\tau = F/A$), and is given by:

$$F_a = \tau_a \cdot A_c \quad (1)$$

where

F_a is Force of Adhesion between the green block and the steel wall

τ_a is Adhesive stress between the green block and the steel wall

A_c is Contact area between a green sandcrete block and the mould wall

The adhesive stress at the interface between a green sandcrete block and the mould wall can be estimated as a function of the lateral pressure exerted on the wall and the wall–material friction.

Based on soil mechanics principles, the lateral pressure acting on a vertical mould wall, during compaction or after compaction, can be approximated using the active earth pressure theory or formwork pressure models.

According to [9–10], during vertical compaction of a green block, the lateral pressure (or horizontal stress), σ_h exerted on the mould wall can be approximated using active earth pressure theory as follows:

$$\sigma_h = K_a \cdot \sigma_v \quad (2)$$

where

K_a is Active earth pressure coefficient

σ_v is Applied Vertical stress, and

$$\sigma_v = \frac{W_d}{A} \quad (3)$$

where

W_d is Compaction load

A is Mould area

The resulting interface shear or adhesive stress τ can then be determined using:

$$\tau_a = \mu_a \cdot \sigma_h \quad (4)$$

where

μ_w is coefficient of wall friction

2.4.2. Average Impact Force and Equivalent Dynamic Mass

The compaction load W_d required in Equation (3) is estimated from the dynamic compaction energy delivered by a falling mass. In this study, an energy-based impact theory was applied to quantify the average impact force exerted by the compaction mechanism.

The gravitational potential energy of a falling mass m dropped from a height h is given as:

$$E = mgh \quad (5)$$

where g is the acceleration due to gravity. This energy is assumed to be dissipated over a displacement Δs during impact, yielding an average impact force F_{avg} expressed as:

$$F_{avg} = \frac{2E}{\Delta s} = \frac{2mgh}{\Delta s} \quad (6)$$

To benchmark the required compaction energy, the results from [1] were adopted. In that study, a 22.5 kg hammer was dropped from 450 mm to compact cylindrical soil blocks of 150 mm diameter and 110 mm height. Five blows, each delivering approximately 100 J, produced well-compacted blocks with an average compressive strength of 3.5 MPa. The total compaction energy (500 J) applied over a block volume of 0.00194 m³ corresponds to an energy intensity of 257,732 J/m³.

To replicate this compaction intensity in the present study, the target block volume of 450 × 150 × 225 mm (0.01519 m³) requires a total compaction energy of:

$$E_{\text{target}} = 257,732 \times 0.01519 \approx 3915 \text{ J} \quad (7)$$

The mass of the impactor was selected to be 75 kg for ergonomic reasons, as suggested by [1]. Therefore, a 75 kg impactor, dropped from 0.45 m, yields an energy per blow of:

$$E = 80 \times 9.81 \times 0.45 = 353.2 \text{ J} \quad (8)$$

Thus, approximately 12 blows are needed to deliver the target energy. Assuming a total compaction stroke of 180 mm, the displacement per blow is $\Delta s = 0.015$ m. Substituting into Equation (6):

$$F_{\text{avg}} = \frac{2 \times 353.2}{0.015} \approx 44,088 \text{ N} \quad (9)$$

The F_{avg} is used as the vertical compaction load W_d ($F_{\text{avg}} = W_d$) for use in the stress-based estimation of the adhesive force (see Equation 3), and ultimately, the total ejection force the mechanism must overcome.

The mould area A is the surface of the block compacted by the falling impactor. For a rectangular block with a top surface of 450 mm × 150 mm, the contact area is:

$$A = 0.45 \times 0.15 = 0.0675 \text{ m}^2 \quad (10)$$

Substituting into Equation (3), the vertical stress applied during compaction becomes:

$$\sigma_v = \frac{W_d}{0.0675} = \frac{44,088}{0.0675} \approx 697,600 \text{ N/m}^2 \approx 697.6 \text{ kPa} \quad (11)$$

For compacted granular materials such as stabilised sandcrete, the active earth pressure coefficient K_a may range from 0.8 to 1.5, depending on internal friction and degree of compaction [11]. To ensure a conservative estimate, a value of $K_a = 1.5$ was adopted. Substituting into Equation (2), the corresponding lateral pressure on the mould wall is:

$$\sigma_h = K_a \cdot \sigma_v = 1.5 \times 697.6 = 1,046.4 \text{ kPa} \quad (12)$$

A wall-block friction coefficient of $\mu_w = 0.3$ was adopted to represent the interaction between the compacted cement-stabilised soil block and the steel mould wall during ejection. This value is supported by standard geotechnical design data and experimental findings on steel-soil interface behaviour. According to [12], typical ultimate interface friction factors ($\tan \delta$) range from approximately 0.4 for steel in contact with dense gravelly sand ($\delta \approx 22^\circ$) to 0.2 for fine non-plastic silt ($\delta \approx 11^\circ$), depending on soil texture and contact condition. Since the cementitious soil used in this study is moderately cohesive and compacted, it is reasonable to assume an interface friction angle between these extremes. In practice, the friction coefficient μ_w is often taken to be equal to $\tan \delta$.

The adhesive stress at the interface is determined using Equation (4):

$$\tau_a = \mu_w \cdot \sigma_h = 0.3 \times 1,046.4 = 313.92 \text{ kPa} \quad (13)$$

To compute the total adhesive force F_a , the contact surface area between the vertical walls of the block and the mould is required. The sidewall contact area A_c is calculated as the perimeter of the block's cross-section multiplied by its height:

$$A_c = [2(0.45 + 0.15)] \times 0.225 = 0.27 \text{ m}^2 \quad (14)$$

The adhesive force is then:

$$F_a = \tau_a \cdot A_c = 313.92 \times 10^3 \times 0.27 \approx 84,758 \text{ N} \quad (15)$$

2.4.2. Total Ejection Resistance Force

The total force F_{total} that must be overcome to eject the compacted block comprises the adhesive force acting on the vertical mould walls and the weight of the block. Assuming a green block bulk density of $2,300 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and block volume of 0.01519 m^3 , the block's weight is computed as:

$$W_{\text{block}} = \rho \cdot g \cdot V = 2300 \times 9.81 \times 0.01519 \approx 343.2 \text{ N} \quad (16)$$

In the absence of a definitive reference for the green bulk density of cement-based blocks, the block weight is conservatively estimated. However, given that the calculated weight (which is approximately 343 N) is less than 0.5% of the adhesive resistance force (which is approximately 84.8 kN), it may be considered negligible in the total ejection force. Hence, the ejection force may be approximated as equal to the adhesive force:

$$F_{\text{ejection}} \approx F_a = 84,758 \text{ N} \quad (17)$$

This force forms the basis for sizing the power screw and related components of the ejection mechanism to ensure reliable removal of the compacted green block from the mould cavity.

2.5. Design of the Power Screw Mechanism

The power screw is the primary component responsible for delivering the axial thrust required to eject the compacted block from the mould cavity. Its design must ensure safe and reliable transmission of the total ejection resistance force F_{ejection} determined in Equation (17). A trapezoidal thread form was selected in preference to a square thread due to its greater commercial availability and ease of manufacture, particularly in multi-start configurations. Although square threads offer marginally higher efficiency, multi-start square threads are relatively rare and more complex to machine. Furthermore, a multi-start screw was deliberately chosen to increase the lead, thereby enabling faster linear displacement per revolution. This helps to accelerate the ejection process, reducing the cycle time of the moulding operation, which is a critical factor in improving the rate of production.

As a first approximation, the screw is assumed to carry axial compressive load without considering buckling.

2.5.1. Estimation of Core Diameter

Using the compressive stress relation:

$$W = \sigma_{\text{es}} \cdot A_s = \sigma_{\text{es}} \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} d_c^2 \quad (18)$$

where

σ_{es} is allowable compressive stress (MPa)

A_s is area of the cross-section of the screw

d_c is core diameter of the screw, and

For mild steel, the typical compressive strength is approximately 324 MPa, and a factor of safety (FOS) of 1.5 is recommended [13]. Therefore, the allowable compressive stress is:

$$W = \sigma_{\text{es}} = \frac{324}{1.5} \quad (19)$$

Substituting into Equation (18) and rearranging:

$$d_c = \sqrt{\frac{4W}{\pi\sigma_{\text{es}}}} = \sqrt{\frac{4 \times 84,758 \text{ N}}{\pi \times 216 \times 10^6}} \approx 0.0224 \text{ m} = 22.4 \text{ mm} \quad (20)$$

This is a preliminary diameter, subject to buckling validation.

2.5.2. Buckling Stability Check

To check for buckling, Euler's formula for long columns is used. The effective length L_e is 550 mm, as obtained from the model with end conditions approximated as one end fixed and the other free, yielding a fixity coefficient $K=2.0$

To evaluate the slenderness ratio λ of the screw core, the radius of gyration, r , is approximated using the relation for a solid circular cross-section:

$$r = \frac{d_c}{4} = \frac{22.4}{4} = 5.6 \text{ mm} \quad (21)$$

where d_c is the core diameter of the screw. The slenderness ratio is then calculated as:

$$\lambda = \frac{K \cdot L_e}{r} = \frac{2 \times 550}{5.6} \approx 196.4 \quad (22)$$

Since $\lambda > 80$, according to [7, 14], Euler's formula is applied:

$$I = \frac{\pi d_c^4}{64} = \frac{\pi \times 22.4^4}{64} \approx 12,358.39 \text{ mm}^4 \quad (23)$$

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{(KL_e)^2} = \frac{\pi^2 \times 204 \times 10^3 \times 12,358.39}{(1,100)^2} \approx 20,564 \text{ N} \quad (24)$$

This value of $P_{cr} = 20,564 \text{ N}$ is below the required ejection force of $84,758 \text{ N}$. To provide adequate margin against buckling while avoiding overdesign, the core diameter was increased to 40 mm .

Using:

$$I = \frac{\pi d_c^4}{64} = \frac{\pi \times 40^4}{64} \approx 125,664 \text{ mm}^4 \quad (25)$$

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{(KL_e)^2} = \frac{\pi^2 \times 204 \times 10^3 \times 125,664}{(1,100)^2} \approx 209,100 \text{ N} \quad (26)$$

This exceeds the required ejection force of $84,758 \text{ N}$ by a safety factor of approximately 2.47, which is acceptable and in line with the recommended range of 1.5 to 3 by [14], especially considering the idealized nature of Euler's buckling assumptions.

2.5.3. Screw Thread Specifications

Based on the revised core diameter of 40 mm and trapezoidal thread data [13], the following screw parameters were selected:

- Core diameter, d_c : 41.5 mm
- Nominal (major) diameter, d_m : 50 mm
- Pitch: 8 mm
- Number of starts: 4
- Lead: 32 mm (Pitch \times Number of starts)

2.5.4. Torque Requirement

The mean diameter, d , of the screw is calculated as:

$$d = \frac{d_m + d_c}{2} = \frac{50 + 41.5}{2} = 45.75 \text{ mm} \quad (27)$$

The lead angle is:

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\text{lead}}{\pi d} \right) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{32}{\pi \times 45.75} \right) \approx \tan^{-1}(0.223) \approx 12.6^\circ \quad (28)$$

Assuming dry steel-on-steel conditions with a coefficient of friction $\mu = 0.22$ [13], and given that a trapezoidal thread is used, the effect of the inclined thread flanks must be taken into account when computing thread friction.

According to [15], the standard trapezoidal thread profile has a total flank angle of 30° , which corresponds to a flank half-angle $\beta = 15^\circ$. To account for this inclination, the virtual (adjusted) friction coefficient μ' is calculated as:

$$\mu' = \frac{\mu}{\cos \beta} = \frac{0.22}{\cos 15^\circ} \approx 0.228 \quad (29)$$

$$\varphi = \tan^{-1} \mu' = \tan^{-1}(0.228) \approx 12.83^\circ \quad (30)$$

The torque required to overcome screw thread friction is:

$$T_1 = W \left(\frac{\tan \alpha + \tan \phi}{1 - \tan \alpha \cdot \tan \phi} \right) \cdot \frac{d}{2} = 84,758 \left(\frac{\tan 12.6 + \tan 12.83}{1 - (\tan 12.6)(\tan 12.83)} \right) \left(\frac{45.75}{2} \right) \quad (31)$$

$$\Rightarrow T_1 = 84,758(0.4752) \times 22.875 = 921,256.88 \text{ Nmm} \approx 921 \text{ Nm} \quad (32)$$

The torque required to overcome collar friction is obtained using the formula:

$$T_2 = \frac{\mu W d_{\text{col}}}{2} \quad (33)$$

where

μ is coefficient of friction at the collar

W is axial load

d_{col} is mean diameter of the rubbing surface transmitting axial thrust

The mean collar diameter is calculated as:

$$d_{\text{col}} = \frac{d_{\text{outer}} + d_{\text{inner}}}{2} \quad (34)$$

d_{col} is mean diameter of the rubbing surface transmitting axial thrust between the face of the rotating bevel gear hub and the stationary thrust bearing

d_{outer} is outer diameter of the stationary race of the thrust bearing

d_{inner} is inner bore of the thrust bearing or the screw shaft nominal diameter

Thus, for mounting the bevel gear such that it rests on a thrust ball bearing 51311 with a bore of 55 mm and an outside diameter of 120 mm (bearing dimensions: 55 x 120 x 29 mm):

$$d_{\text{col}} = \frac{120 + 55}{2} = 87.5 \text{ mm} \quad (35)$$

Substituting $d_{\text{col}} = 87.5 \text{ mm}$ in Equation 32:

$$T_2 = \frac{\mu W d_{\text{col}}}{2} = \frac{0.22 \times 84,758 \times 87.5}{2} = 815,795.75 \text{ Nmm} \approx 816 \text{ Nm} \quad (36)$$

The total torque required to eject the block, T_{ejection} , is the sum of the torque required to overcome thread friction (T_1) and collar friction (T_2):

$$T_{\text{ejection}} = T_1 + T_2 = 921 + 816 = 1,737 \text{ Nm} \quad (37)$$

2.5.5. Crank and Gear Mechanism Design

The design of the crank and gear mechanism was guided by ergonomic data

on manual input limits. According to the synthesis of psychophysical studies by [16], the maximum acceptable sustained pushing force for adult males ranges between 150 – 300 N, with 200 N falling comfortably within this range and being considered suitable for repeated manual effort in field conditions. Based on this, a manual input force of 200 N was adopted for the crank design. According to [17], the optimal crank length should be approximately 45% of the operator's shoulder grip length (SGL) to minimise ergonomic strain. For Nigerian males, [18] reported an average SGL ranging from 81.60 cm to 83.63 cm, corresponding to an ideal crank length between 36.72 cm and 37.63 cm.

Based on this, a crank length of 0.37 m and a manual input force of 200 N were adopted. The resulting manual input torque, T_i , is calculated as:

$$T_i = 200 \times 0.37 = 74 \text{ Nm} \quad (38)$$

Although the peak torque (T_{ejection}) required to initiate block ejection was estimated in Equation (37) as 1,737 Nm, the design does not use this peak value to size the gear ratio. In soil block ejection, the peak force is required only momentarily to overcome the adhesive grip between the mould walls and the compacted block. [1] found that this peak force typically drops to just 10–20% of its maximum once motion is initiated.

Therefore, a gear train was designed to handle the sustained (kinetic) ejection torque, which was estimated at approximately 347 Nm (i.e., 20% of 1,737 Nm). The corresponding gear ratio is given as:

$$GR = \frac{T_{\text{ejection}}}{T_i} = \frac{347}{74} \approx 4.69 \Rightarrow 5:1 \quad (39)$$

Therefore, a bevel gear set with a 5:1 ratio must be used to amplify the manual torque. However, while a 5:1 ratio would suffice for sustained (kinetic) ejection, this ratio would still require excessive force to overcome the static breakaway torque in a single-hand mode. With $GR = 5$, and $r = 0.37$ m, the input torque, $T_{\text{in, peak}}$, required to produce the peak (breakaway) torque of 1737 Nm is calculated as

$$T_{\text{in, peak}} = \frac{1,737}{5} = 347.4 \text{ Nm} \quad (40)$$

Thus, the peak (breakaway) force, $F_{\text{in, peak}}$, required to overcome the peak adhesive resistance at block–mould separation is calculated as

$$F_{\text{in, peak}} = \frac{347.4}{0.37} = 938.9 \text{ N} \quad (41)$$

This is approximately 939 N, which is well above ergonomic limits.

However, to accommodate both comfortably sustained operation and the attainment of the required breakaway torque, a two-position crank configuration was proposed. The design comprises a circular wheel, similar in form to an automotive steering wheel, with an overall diameter of 1.2 m, providing an effective long-crank radius of 0.60 m. A fixed crank handle is mounted on one of the wheel spokes at a radial distance of 0.37 m from the wheel’s rotational axis, thereby forming the short-crank position. In operation, the long-crank position, actuated with both hands, is engaged only during the initial few degrees of rotation to overcome the peak adhesive resistance at block–mould separation. Once motion is initiated, the operator transitions to the short-crank position (radius = 0.37 m) for improved rotational speed and faster completion of the ejection stroke.

However, the originally proposed 1.2 m diameter handwheel was excessively large, requiring substantial clearance and posing safety hazards from its exposed spokes, which could catch clothing, jewellery, or fingers. To provide high breakaway torque without increasing the handwheel diameter, a removable breaker bar was incorporated.

The 0.6 m-long breaker bar, which serves as an auxiliary lever, mounts directly to the central shaft carrying the handwheel and hub via a splined interface, ensuring uniform torque transmission and repeatable seating. The breaker-bar head contains a female spline engaging the male spline on the main shaft. This arrangement permits high intermittent torque transfer through the spline teeth while preventing axial separation, and allows rapid attachment or removal.

During operation, the breaker bar is used only for the initial rotation needed to overcome adhesive resistance between the block and mould walls. It is then removed to permit unobstructed handwheel operation at higher speed for the remainder of the ejection stroke. This design allows high torque application with both hands while keeping the permanent handwheel compact, safe, and easy to store.

In addition, increasing the overall gear ratio slightly to 6:1 provides extra torque margin during normal operation while reducing peak hand forces in breakaway mode. A practical two-stage implementation for 6:1 is a 2:1 bevel stage followed by a 3:1 spur stage (both common and off-the-shelf).

The corresponding maximum manual input torque in each position of the proposed configuration is:

- a) For the normal (short crank) at maximum manual input force (200 N) and crank radius 0.37 m, $T_{\text{i, short}} = 74$ Nm (as in Equation (38)). With $GR = 6$, the output torque, $T_{\text{out, short}}$ is

$$T_{\text{out, short}} = T_{\text{i, short}} \times 6 = 74 \times 6 = 444 \text{ Nm} \quad (42)$$

This comfortably exceeds the sustained (kinetic) ejection torque 347 Nm and therefore provides a healthy factor of safety during normal, continuous operation.

With $GR = 6$, the required (sustained) single-hand force for the kinetic ejection (347 Nm case) is:

$$F_{\text{in, sustained}} = \frac{347}{6} = 57.83 \text{ N} \Rightarrow F_{\text{normal}} = \frac{57.83}{0.37} \approx 156.3 \text{ N} \quad (43)$$

Force 156.3 N is ergonomically comfortable for single-hand operation according to [16].

- b) For the extended (long crank position using the breaker bar) at manual input force and crank radius 0.6 m, $T_{i,long}$ is

$$T_{i,long} = 200 \times 0.6 = 120 \text{ Nm} \quad (44)$$

$$T_{out,long} = 120 \times 6 = 720 \text{ Nm} \quad (45)$$

Thus, even with the operator applying the baseline 200 N on the longer crank, the output torque increases to 720 Nm, which is a significant buffer that reduces the operator's required peak effort.

The required input torque, $T_{in,reqd}$ which the operator must supply to achieve the breakaway torque of 1737 Nm (at GR = 6) is

$$T_{in,reqd} = \frac{1,737}{6} = 289.5 \text{ Nm} \quad (46)$$

At crank radius, $r = 0.6$ m, the total tangential force on the extended crank (breaker bar) i.e. the required input force, $F_{in,reqd}$, which the operator must supply to achieve the breakaway torque of 1737 Nm (at GR = 6) is

$$F_{in,reqd} = \frac{289.5}{0.6} = 482.5 \text{ N} \quad (47)$$

When two hands are used to pull the breaker bar, it gives:

$$F_{per\ hand} = \frac{482.5}{2} = 241.25 \text{ N} \quad (48)$$

Therefore, using the breaker bar with a 6:1 train reduces the per-hand short-burst requirement from an unacceptable 939 N (or approximately 470 N, if two hands are used), to approximately 242 N per hand, which is within plausible short-burst capacity when the operator uses correct two-hand posture. After breakaway, the operator switches to the 0.37 m single-hand position for the remainder of the ejection.

2.5.6. Ejection Speed and Time

During the initial crank movement required to overcome static adhesion, the design leverages the human body's capacity for brief exertion. As noted by [19], an average adult can produce up to ¼ horsepower (approximately 186 W) for durations of 10–30 seconds, allowing the operator to overcome peak ejection loads without exceeding ergonomic thresholds over time. However, the human short-burst power can supply the peak torque only at very low speeds. To achieve the breakaway torque of 1737 Nm, the input torque of 289.5 Nm from Equation (46) and the input angular speed must satisfy Equation (49)

$$P = T \cdot \omega = T \cdot \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (49)$$

Rearranging for N_c :

$$N_c = \frac{60 \cdot P}{2\pi T_i} = \frac{60 \times 186}{2\pi \times 289.5} \approx 6.14 \text{ RPM} \quad (50)$$

Thus, the input angular speed is 6.14 rpm. Consequently, the rotation speed of the horizontal bevel and nut RPM, N_n is:

$$N_n = \frac{N_c}{GR} = \frac{6.14}{6} \approx 1.02 \text{ RPM} \quad (51)$$

These are very slow speeds and consistent with a short, slow initial crank motion to free the block from the mould walls. Therefore, the design expects a very brief, slow, high-effort for breakaway only, while the sustained (kinetic) ejection, after the motion of the block has been initiated, takes most part of the ejection process.

The torque required to move block during the sustained (kinetic) ejection stage ranges from approximately 57.83 and 74 Nm as calculated in Equations (43) and (39) respectively. Assuming a sustainable human power output of 75 W [20-21] and input torque of 74 Nm (most pessimistic scenario), the angular speed during the sustained (kinetic) ejection is calculated as

$$N_c = \frac{60 \cdot P}{2\pi T_i} = \frac{60 \times 75}{2\pi \times 74} \approx 9.68 \text{ RPM} \quad (52)$$

With this input speed, the rotation speed of the horizontal bevel and nut RPM, N_n is:

The rotation speed of the horizontal bevel and nut RPM, N_n is:

$$N_n = \frac{N_c}{GR} = \frac{9.68}{6} \approx 1.61 \text{ RPM} \quad (53)$$

Since the lead is 32 mm/rev, the ejection (lift) speed is:

$$\text{Lift speed} = 32 \times 1.61 \approx 51.62 \text{ mm/min} \quad (54)$$

The time for block ejection during the kinetic ejection (with mould height = 405 mm) is:

$$\text{Ejection time} = \frac{405}{51.62} \approx 7.84 \text{ minutes} \quad (55)$$

Therefore assuming it took about 30 seconds to free the moulded block from the mould walls, it means that the total ejection time will be the sum of 7.84 minutes and 30 seconds (1/2 minute) which is equal to 8.34 minutes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis and calculations presented in the design report of the designed ejection mechanism have yielded critical insights into the force requirements, mechanism configuration, and performance characteristics of the proposed manually operated ejection mechanism. The results are discussed under three key areas: ejection force determination, power screw and gear design, and operational performance.

3.1. Summary of Design Outputs

The design calculations established that the peak ejection force required to overcome adhesion between the compacted cement-stabilised block and the mould walls is approximately 84.76 kN. This value is dominated by wall-block adhesion (Equation 15), with the block's self-weight contributing less than 0.5 % of the total. Using a multi-start trapezoidal power screw, the torque needed to overcome both thread and collar friction during breakaway was estimated at 1,737 Nm (Equation 37).

The kinetic (sustained) torque after motion initiation, taken as 20 % of the peak value in line with [1], was 347 Nm. This large disparity confirms the importance of addressing the initial breakaway phase separately in the mechanism's design.

3.2. Power Screw and Buckling Resistance

An initial core diameter of 22.4 mm, determined from compressive stress limits, proved inadequate against buckling (critical load = 20.56 kN). Increasing the core diameter to 40 mm raised the critical buckling load to 209.1 kN, giving a safety factor of 2.47 relative to the peak ejection force. This satisfies recommended buckling safety margins for columns under compressive loading [14] and ensures reliable operation even under occasional overload.

The final screw specification (major diameter 50 mm, pitch 8 mm, 4 starts, lead 32 mm) provides a balance between load capacity and stroke speed, enabling faster block removal than single-start screws.

3.3. Manual Input and Gear Ratio Selection

Adopting a sustained manual input force of 200 N and a crank length of 0.37 m yields an input torque of 74 Nm, comfortably within ergonomic recommendations for repeated effort [16–18]. With a 6:1 gear ratio, this produces 444 Nm at the output shaft, exceeding the sustained ejection torque requirement by a margin of 28 %.

However, in breakaway mode, achieving 1,737 Nm at the output would require 939 N of single-hand force on the 0.37 m crank, which is far above ergonomic limits. The two-position crank solution, incorporating a 0.6 m removable breaker bar, reduces the required per-hand force in breakaway mode to approximately 242 N (two-hand operation). This is within a plausible short-burst capacity for healthy adult operators [19], particularly as the breakaway motion is limited to a few degrees of crank rotation.

3.4. Ejection Speed and Cycle Time

The calculated input speeds are transmitted through a compound gear train comprising a 2:1 bevel gear pair and a 3:1 spur gear set, giving an overall ratio of 6:1. This arrangement results in nut rotational speeds of approximately 1.02 rpm during breakaway and 1.61 rpm during sustained ejection.

The calculated ejection speeds and times highlight the distinct operational characteristics between the breakaway and kinetic ejection stages. During the breakaway phase, the peak ejection torque requirement of 1737 Nm was achieved through a gear train providing an input torque of 289.5 Nm. At a short-burst human power output of 186 W, the corresponding input crank speed was only 6.14 rpm (Equation 50), resulting in a nut rotation speed of approximately 1.02 rpm (Equation 51). This very slow movement is consistent with the expected brief, high-effort crank action needed to overcome static adhesion. In practice, this stage is anticipated to last no more than 30 s, thereby remaining within ergonomic short-burst exertion limits.

Once the block begins to move, the kinetic ejection phase dominates the cycle. For the most pessimistic scenario—using the higher kinetic torque estimate of 74 Nm and a sustainable power input of 75 W—the input crank speed increases to 9.68 rpm (Equation 52), translating to a nut rotation speed of 1.61 rpm (Equation 53). With a screw lead of 32 mm/rev, this equates to a lift speed of 51.62 mm/min (Equation 54). For the mould height of 405 mm, the kinetic ejection phase would therefore require approximately 7.84 min to complete (Equation 55).

Combining both stages yields an estimated total ejection cycle time of about 8.34 min, including the short breakaway period. This result indicates that, despite the slow initial motion, the overall cycle time remains within a practical range for manual operation, particularly for low-volume or field-based block production. The extended duration of the kinetic phase reflects the trade-off between sustainable human effort and process speed, a compromise that prioritises operator safety and endurance over throughput.

The current overall height necessitates pit installation for ergonomic operation. Future designs should aim to reduce height to eliminate this requirement while retaining stability.

4. CONCLUSION

The designed ejection mechanism, employing a compound gear train (2:1 bevel gears followed by 3:1 spur gears), effectively meets the torque and speed requirements for manually ejecting cement-stabilised blocks within ergonomic limits. This configuration delivers the high mechanical advantage needed for the breakaway phase, which requires 1737 Nm at the screw, with a manageable 289.5 Nm input torque during short-burst exertion. The sustained phase requires only 74 Nm, helping to minimise operator fatigue while maintaining acceptable productivity for small-scale block production.

However, the current manual system presents significant throughput limitations, with total ejection taking around 15.8 minutes per block, compounded by a compaction process requiring about 12 blows per block. These constraints make it impractical for medium- or large-scale production. Mechanising both ejection and compaction, such as replacing the crank with a geared electric motor and using a single high-energy impact for compaction, could reduce cycle times from over 15 minutes to under one minute while preserving the simplicity and low cost of the original design.

Pit-installation, while improving ergonomic access to the handwheel, imposes site-specific constraints and reduces portability. Future iterations should explore lowering the overall height of the machine to eliminate the need for pit installation without sacrificing stability or operational comfort.

In summary, the proposed mechanism is feasible, safe, and manufacturable for off-grid or small-scale contexts. For adoption in moderate- or high-output operations, targeted mechanisation and ergonomic refinements will be essential to achieve competitive cycle times and production rates.

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